

The Platypuses of Art

Unclassifiable Practices and a Media Archive in Chile

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ABSTRACT

This article offers a critical and historical review of media arts in Chile, addressing their emergence, development, and the challenges of their inscription within the artistic field. From a situated genealogical perspective, it analyzes practices that intertwine art, science, and technology, highlighting both their growing institutional visibility and the difficulties surrounding their categorization and recognition within national art historiography. Using the figure of the "platypus" as a metaphor for the unclassifiable, the article proposes a reflection on the tensions between practice and theory, the persistence of exclusionary disciplinary models, and the need to expand interpretative frameworks to understand these cross-border experiences. It considers both pioneering and current cases and draws on theoretical references from science and technology studies, decolonial thought, technoscientific feminisms, and posthumanism. Overall, it underscores the urgency of constructing critical narratives that account for these practices as an integral—though historically marginalized—part of contemporary artistic production in Chile.

Keywords

Media Arts, Art and Technology, Art History in Chile, Transdisciplinarity, Platypus

1 Introduction

ACM's In recent decades, the development of media arts has shaped a dynamic and expansive field where aesthetic, technological, and scientific explorations converge. This expansion—observable both in the growth of institutional initiatives and in the diversity of formats, languages, and materialities—has generated a series of critical and conceptual challenges that question traditional categories of art. In Chile, the proliferation of festivals, laboratories, collaborative platforms, and collectives has helped to consolidate an active media ecosystem, although still scarcely documented from a historical and analytical perspective.

This work proposes a panoramic and situated review of the media arts field in Chile, attending both to its genealogy and the conceptual tensions that have accompanied its development. Central questions include: How has this field historically taken shape, and what narratives have been left out of the official histories of art? What discursive, political, or material strategies have artists working at the intersection of art, science, and technology deployed? How do these often marginal or unclassifiable practices challenge prevailing notions of authorship, medium, craft, and experimentation in contemporary art?

The methodology combines a critical bibliographic review of national and international texts, analysis of emblematic case studies, in-depth interviews with artists and curators, and the construction of an open digital archive: www.arteymedios.org. This repository seeks to gather, systematize, and circulate dispersed or hard-to-access information about works, artists, and initiatives that articulate art, science, and technology in Chile, with particular attention to experimental, collaborative, and decentralized experiences.

Through the metaphor of the platypus, this work offers a critical reflection on the unclassifiable condition of media arts, highlighting their cross-border potential and their capacity to reconfigure the links between aesthetics, technique, and knowledge, as well as to imagine alternative futures from a technopolitical and situated perspective.

2 What is Visible and What is Absent: Experimental Practices and Pending Narratives

Currently, artistic practices that use resources, references, and methodologies from various intersections

with the sciences (biological, mathematical, physical) and technologies (analog and digital) have gained increasing momentum. This observation can be confirmed by the proliferation of specific events in this area and the considerable growth in their audiences. In Chile, initiatives such as the Bienal de Artes Mediales, the Tsunami Festival of Sound Art, the Toda la Teoría del Universo Festival, and the Lumen Art and New Media Encounter have become significant landmarks in the cultural calendar.

This growth has gone hand in hand with new critical approaches emerging from philosophy, anthropology, history, and the social sciences. These perspectives have nourished both artistic creation and thought around it, including actor-network theory [4, 5], new materialisms [2, 6], decolonial thought [10, 9], and posthumanism [1, 8].

Despite the significant rise of these practices, they have not been sufficiently addressed in a systematic way from the standpoint of art history and theory. In Chile, there are no books that have studied the relationship between art, science, and technology from a historical and analytical perspective focused on its specificity. This is not surprising, as there have also been few historical-theoretical attempts to describe national contemporary artistic production more broadly. While a large number of monographic essays or exhibition catalogues can be traced, until quite recently there were no texts addressing the topic in a panoramic way. To date, *Copiar el Edén* [19] and *Chile Arte Extremo: nuevas tendencias en el cambio de siglo* [20] are among the few attempts to describe this specific period of prolific production, though it displays vast conceptual, aesthetic, and formal differences. In the field of media arts, there is only the book *Apuntes para una historia del video en Chile* [16], which devotes just a brief section to video art, privileging instead the use of this medium in other independent genres such as journalistic documentary, and covering only a limited period: from the 1970s to the 1990s. Another relevant publication is *Sonidos Visibles: Antecedentes y desarrollo del Arte Sonoro en Chile* [17], which also seeks to provide a broad and general perspective on sound experimentation, referring only to a few works involving technology from the 1970s to the present. A text that also merits attention is *En el principio: arte, archivos y tecnologías durante la dictadura en Chile* [21], which addresses some moments in the early development of media arts in Chile, though from a critical stance regarding the dispersion of their

archives. A more recent contribution is the book *Visiones Laterales. Cine y Video experimental en Chile 1957–2017* [15], which analyzes audiovisual artistic production from the mid-twentieth century to 2017. Even so, there are no published texts that address other areas of experimentation involving intersections with science and technology on a broader level. To date, the most exhaustive effort to describe and highlight the specificity of these practices has been the thesis *Arte de los Medios y transformaciones sociales en Chile durante la transición política* [13], but its temporal scope excludes the exponential growth of digital technologies related to big data, the application of artificial intelligence, and the mass use of mobile devices. This scarcity of narrative about contemporary production is likely due to the difficulties involved in defining this specific field.

3 On the Designation of the Field

“Media Art,” “Medial Arts,” “Art and New Media,” “Electronic Art,” “Digital Art,” “Cyberart,” “Transmedia Art” are some of the terms used to group or describe the diversity of practices that began to emerge with increasing visibility in the second half of the 20th century. These practices are characterized by the experimental and creative use of electronic and digital technologies, and later expanded their reach by incorporating approaches and languages from the biological, physical, chemical, and social sciences. This diversity of manifestations shares an experimental vocation and can hardly be reduced to a single style or program. That is, each of the different trends observable in this subfield of contemporary art develops distinct processes and presents varied formal, discursive, and material characteristics [11]. The names by which we know them may seem synonymous, but they are not equivalent. Some focus on their supports (electronic, digital, biological, organic, cybernetic, mechanical); others on their devices (computer art, net art, robotics, cinema, video); still others on their operational modes (interactive art, generative art, data visualization, mapping), or more generally are defined by the supposed novelty they entail. In this sense, the term “new media,” popular since the 1990s and originally used to describe the impact of computing and video on our lives, may be the most problematic and questionable, as paradoxically the “new” refers to devices that become prematurely obsolete [14]. The technological devices that surround us

age and are discarded at an unprecedented speed, not because of their structure or functionality, but most often because of the mandate imposed by the market, which uses the concept of “innovation” as both a brand and an end in itself.

The nomenclatures used to designate this unstable and ever-shifting field of production always seem insufficient and pose a persistent challenge. Sociology, history, and art theory almost always seem to arrive too late in the face of the disciplinary overflow brought on by the new formal and technical possibilities offered by emerging languages, technological supports, and scientific challenges for artists. As digital art curator and theorist Christiane Paul notes, “technologies develop much faster than the rhetorics that describe them in their social, economic, and aesthetic dimension” [7]. This apparent gap between praxis and theory poses a major challenge for the disciplines that seek to narrate, systematize, analyze, and reflect upon artistic practices. But this problem is also evident in the more conventional and hegemonic fields of art. Even today, it remains uncomfortable to find a widely accepted definition for the term “art” itself, and the picture becomes even more complex with the use of compound terms that seek to delineate areas, categories, languages, and artistic genres. According to the standard art history books, for a long time the dominant expression was “fine arts,” whose inscription in the 18th century attempted to establish a separation from utilitarian crafts—also called “servile” or applied arts [18]. However, the rapid transformations in representational forms throughout the 19th century—resulting from political, economic, social, and also technical changes—would lead to the collapse of the “fine arts” designation, which was replaced, not without controversy, by the contemporary label “visual arts”. This label, again, proves insufficient, as it excludes practices such as sound art or those centered on tactile, olfactory, or kinesthetic perceptions, or whose aim lies in the production of knowledge.

4 Art’s Platypuses: Unclassifiable Creatures at the Intersection of Science and Aesthetics

Artists who work with technological devices and draw from scientific inquiry often provoke confusion. They are frequently mistaken for engineers, activists, or inventors

[22]. Their work seems to escape the traditional categories of the art field—as though they were specimens absent from a naturalist’s catalogue. When Europeans first encountered a platypus in 1798, they believed it to be an elaborate hoax by a taxidermist. They searched for seams, suspecting that this strange creature from Tasmania was nothing more than a Frankenstein-like monster made from parts of other animals. Indeed, the platypus is a curious animal, with a “rare” constitution: it has a duck-like bill, a beaver-like tail, and an otter-like body. It is semi-aquatic, bioluminescent, a mammal that lays eggs; it is timid, playful, and venomous, and it possesses more than 40,000 electroreceptors that allow it to detect the electric field of its prey. In other words, it is an animal that eludes any known classification, any taxonomic order. Media artists may provoke a similar perplexity among audiences and critics. For a long time, the history and theory of art taught us to believe that science, aesthetics, and technology were distant realms. As a result, a wide range of artifacts, projects, and inventions were left out of the narrative constructed by art history to define a narrow and exclusive idea of what counts as art.

The construction of automata—documented since antiquity or in the writings of Giovanni Fontana in the 15th century; Athanasius Kircher’s magic lantern in the 17th century; Leonardo da Vinci’s inverted waterfalls; or the many optical machines that preceded the invention of the daguerreotype and cinematograph—were proposals either omitted or marginalized by art history and aesthetics. In a similar fashion, artistic representations from non-European regions were excluded, dismissed as “craft” rather than “fine art.” These omissions and dismissals persisted well into the twentieth century. Nearly a hundred years ago, Marcel Duchamp himself—vanguard artist *par excellence*, known for his readymades—also created a series of strange devices (less acknowledged by the canon that celebrates him) that incorporated motors and generated optical illusions through the spinning of images: Rotative Plaques Verre (1920) and Rotary Demisphere (1925). In 1935, Duchamp extended this optical-aesthetic project by entering a competition for amateur inventors, presenting cardboard discs printed with lithographed drawings meant to be spun on a phonograph. His novel proposal went completely unnoticed by the public, as his invention was an “unidentified object,” useless—or, as described by his friend Gabrielle Buffet-Picabia, lacking a “civil status” and therefore “impossible to classify for

scholars of aesthetics and urgent reason” [3]. Indeed, this lack of disciplinary inscription has long accompanied cross-border projects linking art, science, and technology.

Years later, in the 1960s, philosopher Gilbert Simondon would again use a legal metaphor to refer to technological objects: “Culture is unbalanced because it recognizes certain objects, such as the aesthetic object, and grants them citizenship in the world of meanings, while rejecting other objects, particularly technical ones” [12].

These cross-border arts have had to assume their marginal or eccentric condition. Although much time has passed since the 1960s—when, in the context of the emergence of computers and video, connections began to form between the scientific, technological, and artistic worlds through initiatives like E.A.T. Experiments in Art and Technology (1966), promoted by Bell Industries in the United States, or when Argentine artist Marta Minujín presented her piece *Simultaneidad en Simultaneidad* at the Instituto Torcuato di Tella in Buenos Aires, using the media of the time (television, telephone, radio, satellite)—techno-artistic experimentation continues to be met with suspicion or misunderstanding.

5 Media Arts in Chile

In our country, there have been many artists since the 20th century who could well have been identified as platypuses. In 1960, Juan Carlos Martinoya and Nahum Joel built the *Abstractoscopio cromático*, a kind of robot that, combining electronics, cybernetics, and crystallography, was able to project a wide range of visual compositions. Matilde Pérez incorporated electric motors into her kinetic sculptures and built the *Túnel Cinético* (1970), which allowed viewers to pass through it among effects produced by mirrors, lights, and geometric figures. In the same decade, Alejandro Siña worked with electromechanical elements; he studied at the Center for Advanced Visual Studies (CAVS) at MIT in the United States and experimented not only with the use of neon but also with its fabrication. In 1978, José Vicente Asuar invented the COMDASUAR, a hybrid-technology computer that enabled the performance of music. In the United States, Enrique Castro-Cid combined mathematics and planimetry (originally developed for aircraft design) to represent theories of physics, and inspired by cybernetics, he built strange anthropomorphic robots using discarded industrial parts,

air compressors, electromagnets, and film projectors. In the 1970s, Gonzalo Mezza ventured into video art, installation, and the use of Polaroids and photocopiers; for his part, Juan Downey is not only considered one of the pioneers of video art but also stood out for his explorations in computer science, cybernetics, telematics, and “invisible energy” (radiation, seismic vibrations, radio and radar waves), seeking to establish connections between society, history, environment, and identity [13].

In the following decades, all these artists—unclassifiable in their time and whose work was often overlooked or dismissed by academia—found in the label ‘media arts’ a space of convergence. Initiatives such as the Bienal de Artes Mediales (dating back to 1993); the Matilde Pérez competition; the Primavera Hacker meeting; the Anilla MAC space; the regional gatherings LUMEN (Punta Arenas), Norte Medial (Antofagasta), Toda La Teoría del Universo (Concepción), and Tsonami (Valparaíso), have created platforms for exchange, training, and visibility for artists working across these disciplinary intersections.

While it may seem excessive to assign qualifiers to contemporary artistic practices, the adjective “medial,” as used in Latin America—especially in Chile—has proven useful. The field of media arts has demonstrated remarkable dynamism, not only in terms of crossing disciplines, but also in contributing to critical, philosophical, political, and even socio-economic reflection on our time. It has allowed us to question the technoscientific predeterminations fostered by the digitalization of our lives and has invited us to imagine other im/possible futures.

6 Some Contemporary Platypuses

Among the contemporary artists whose work paradigmatically embodies the platypus-like condition of media arts are Constanza Piña, Natacha Cabellos Ricart, Nicole L’Huillier, and Daniel Cruz. Far from belonging to a single disciplinary field, their work moves between technological experimentation, aesthetic sensitivity, and critical thought. However, alongside these forms of hybridity between art, science, and technology, another equally unclassifiable current has emerged in recent years: that of those who reactivate ancestral knowledge through a medial lens, engaging with Indigenous cosmologies, ritual techniques, and native technologies.

This current—which we might call ancestral platypuses—broadens the medial spectrum by incorporating a cosmopolitical, affective, and spiritual dimension into technoscience.

Constanza Piña, also known as Corazón de Robota, is a clear example of this crossing between electronic art, feminist genealogy, and ancestral knowledge. Her project *Khipu* (2014–), conceived as a long-term research endeavor, revives the ancient Andean system of cords and knots as a form of coding and oracle. Using wool and copper threads as sonic and tactile antennas, Piña creates installations that allow us to “hear the voices of the void,” exploring other possible genealogies for computing and memory technologies from a decolonial, situated, and feminist perspective. The act of spinning, amplifying, and resonating with the past from a collaborative laboratory embodies the figure of the platypus as an assemblage of dissonant knowledges.

Natacha Cabellos Ricart, for her part, shifts the focus toward technopoetic ecology. In works such as *Laboratorio de afectos para una planta migrante* (2019), a robotic hand caresses an aloe plant while sensors translate the contact into data visualizations. Her practice dismantles binary oppositions between nature and artifice, plant and machine, making visible the affective dimension of the non-human. From a posthuman and ecofeminist aesthetic, her work proposes forms of symbiotic coexistence between organic bodies and sensitive technologies.

In the case of Nicole L’Huillier, the intersection of sound art, science fiction, and technological spirituality takes the form of a kind of cosmic witchcraft. Works such as *Telemetron*, *Soledad*, and *Paracantora* are sonic and performative devices that connect data, residues, frequencies, and memories. In collaboration with other artists—as in *Resonaciones* (2022)—she has worked on reactivating Moche whistling vessels alongside Francisca Gili and healer Karen Urcia, proposing a medial mode of listening grounded in the Andean reciprocity of *ayni*. Here, technique is not merely machine: it is ceremony, vibrant memory, and cohabitation with the non-human.

Daniel Cruz, meanwhile, approaches the medial condition through a critical archaeology of contemporary control infrastructures. In *Espesores Tisulares*, he explores how information and surveillance systems shape our bodies and desires. Cruz acts as a techno-spy tracking the invisible flows of algorithmic power, staging the hidden matter of global digitalization: cables, data, dust, bodies, memory.

To these profiles we can add the emerging category of the ancestral platypus, a figure that finds resonance in the work of Francisca Gili. In the project *Cantarino*, Gili does not use technology as an instrumental medium, but rather as a form of sensory and cosmopolitical reactivation. Working with pre-Hispanic whistling vessels from the Moche culture, she does not conceive of them as archaeological remnants but as “ceramic beings,” sonorous entities capable of affecting the present. Through sensors, synthesis systems, and immersive performances, Gili listens to and translates these silenced voices, integrating shamanic practices, contemporary technologies, and Andean epistemologies. Her work situates itself within what Yuk Hui has called *cosmotronics*, what Silvia Rivera Cusicanqui names *ch’ixi* [10], or what Elvira Espejo proposes as *crianza mutua*: ways of thinking about technique beyond modern binary logic, as a vital network interweaving bodies, memory, affect, and territory.

In sum, the platypuses of media art in Chile not only destabilize disciplinary categories but also allow us to imagine other possible maps for art, where technique might be a fabric, a sound, a ritual choreography, or a gesture of care. In times of automation and planned obsolescence, perhaps the most radical act is not to invent the new, but to reactivate that which never truly left.

7 Conclusions

The platypuses of media art in Chile represent not merely an aesthetic anomaly but a powerful critical reservoir in response to the regimes of classification, archiving, and legitimation in contemporary art. Their practices do not fit within traditional taxonomies precisely because they emerge from border-crossing territories: between art and science, between invention and ritual, between technology and memory. But also between the visible and that which has been historically omitted.

Far from being mere eccentricities, these practices respond to deep and situated genealogies—often embodied in ancestral knowledge, vernacular technologies, or non-Western cosmologies—that challenge the linearity of technical progress imposed by hegemonic models. In this regard, concepts such as *cosmotronics* by Yuk Hui (2020), *ch’ixi* by Silvia Rivera Cusicanqui (2015), or *crianza mutua* by Elvira Espejo (2019) operate not only as theoretical frameworks but as

ways of making, inhabiting, and resisting through media art.

In the face of a field still unevenly narrated, initiatives like PAM / Plataforma Arte y Medios have proven essential. Created nearly a decade ago, PAM has aimed to collect, document, and circulate a fragmented history: works, artists, devices, writings, and processes that would otherwise have remained outside official narratives. Rather than a closed archive, PAM functions as a living, open, and ever-evolving space that embraces disciplinary overflow as a methodology and media memory as a political act.

Like the platypus, these practices escape the natural order of things—not because they are monstrous, but because they reveal that what is considered ‘natural’—even in art—has been an exclusionary construction that we can now dismantle, wire by wire. Perhaps the most challenging—and promising—aspect of media arts in Chile is not what they represent, but what they disrupt.

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